

Serum endocannabinoid levels in suicide attempters: A pilot study

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Abstract

The search for a biomarker for suicide risk is a longstanding pursuit in clinical psychiatry. Literature addressing the role of endocannabinoids in suicide attempters (SA) is sparse. This cross-sectional study is aimed at comparing 8 AM serum concentrations of 4 endogenous cannabinoids (anandamide, AEA; 2-arachidonoylglycerol, 2-AG; N-palmitoiletanolamida, PEA; and oleoylethanolamide, OEA) in 30 suicide attempters (SA) and 12 psychiatric controls (PC). 8 AM AEA and PEA serum levels were higher in SA compared to PC without controlling for cannabis use ($n = 42$) (3.58 ± 5.77 vs. 1.62 ± 2.49 , $F = 3.04$, $P = 0.089$; and 3.31 ± 4.82 vs. 1.21 ± 1.20 , $F = 6.22$, $p = 0.017$, respectively). Serum ACTH was higher in PC compared to SA (32.11 ± 21.60 vs. 20.05 ± 9.96 , $F = 9.031$, $p = 0.005$). After controlling for cannabis use in the urine test ($n = 28$), 8 AM AEA and PEA serum levels remained higher in SA compared to PC (4.57 ± 6.38 vs. 0.64 ± 1.11 , $F = 4.852$, $P = 0.037$; and 4.35 ± 5.46 vs. 1.21 ± 1.25 , $F = 4.125$, $p = 0.053$, respectively). The present study offers preliminary evidence about the role of AEA and PEA in suicidal behavior (SB). Furthermore, in the context of the mental pain model of SB, our findings suggest that some endocannabinoids may play a role in the pathophysiology of SB. Our pilot study deserves replication by other studies with bigger sample sizes.

Keywords: Endocannabinoids; Anandamide; 2-arachidonoylglycerol; N-palmitoiletanolamida; Oleoylethanolamide; Suicidal behavior

1 Introduction

Nearly one million people suicide every year, and between 10 and 20 million people attempt suicide (WHO, 1999). Suicide attempters (SA) are at increased suicide risk (Parra-Urbe et al., 2017). The search for a biomarker for suicide

risk that may improve suicide risk assessment is a longstanding pursuit of clinical psychiatry (Mann et al., 2006). Traditionally, the serotonin model of suicidal behavior (SB) was the predominant model of suicidology (Mann et al., 1999), and the most relevant biomarkers for estimating suicide risk were: 1) reduced levels of the serotonin metabolite 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid (5-HIAA) in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), reflecting diatheses (trait-dependent risk factors); and 2) non-suppression in the dexamethasone suppression test (DST), reflecting hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis dysfunction to stress (state-dependent factors) (Coryell and Schlesser, 2001; Jokinen et al., 2008). A recent review expanded the topic and included as the most promising biomarkers of SB “for assessing suicide risk in clinical settings” major neurotransmitters such as serotonin, catecholamines, GABA, and glutamate, the HPA axis, lipids, the inflammasome, and neuroplasticity biomarkers (Sudol and Mann, 2017). This is in keeping with our recent critique that the serotonin model might be too simplistic, whereas the psychological pain model is what really unifies SB (de Leon, Baca-Garcia et al., 2015). However, neither the review mentioned above nor our editorial cited the endocannabinoid (EC) system as an interesting system for providing new opportunities for disruptive treatments in patients displaying SB. Unfortunately, there has been very little literature addressing the role of the EC system in major depression and SB (Vinod, 2012) until recently.

Our interest in studying the role of endocannabinoids in SB is based on the following facts: 1) There is mounting evidence suggesting that the EC system is involved in mood regulation (Monteleone et al., 2010) and pain (Ashton and Moore, 2011; Benedetti et al., 2013); accordingly, it is critical to understand such a system (the EC system) if one is defending the impact of mental pain and emptiness on SB (Blasco-Fontecilla et al., 2015; de Leon, Baca-Garcia et al., 2015); 2) the current use of cannabis has reached epidemic proportions in current postmodern societies (Blasco-Fontecilla, 2018); 3) the use of cannabis may have different effects based on gender and doses (Shalit et al., 2016); and 4) the use of Synthetic Cannabinoids is causing different psychopathological profiles that we are still trying to understand and differentiate from the “classical” psychopathological profiles secondary to natural cannabinoids (Shalit et al., 2016; Bassir Nia, Mann et al., 2019).

The EC system includes: 1) endogenous ligands (i.e. anandamide, AEA; N-palmitoylethanolamide, PEA; 2-arachidonoylglycerol, 2-AG; and oleoylethanolamide, OEA); 2) the endocannabinoid degrading enzymes (i.e. fatty acid amide hydrolase, FAAH); and 3) two main cannabinoid receptors (CB₁ and CB₂) (Colino et al., 2018). The CB₁ receptor is mainly found within the central nervous system (CNS) (Howlett, 2002) and is critical in the neuronal circuits that mediate mood, emotion, and motivation (Vinod, 2012). The activation of CB₁ receptors has traditionally been associated with antinociceptive effects. Furthermore, presynaptic CB₁ regulates serotonin and norepinephrine release (Nakazi et al., 2000), and the gene encoding CB₁ (*CNRI*) is down-regulated by steroids (Mailleux and Vanderhaeghen, 1993). CB₂ receptors are mainly peripherally expressed and related to the immune system (Howlett, 2002).

Cannabidiol (CBD), the major phytocannabinoid compound in the *Cannabis sativa* (40% of Cannabis extracts), has antidepressant, anxiolytic, and prohedonic effects in rat models (Shoval et al., 2016; Hen-Shoval et al., 2018). However, there is limited literature on cannabidiolic acid (CBDA), also a major but instable constituent of the *C. sativa* plant. Quite inherently, a recent experiment in 2 rat models testing a chemically stable derivate, the CBDA methyl ester (HU-580), has proven that this agent is a potent anti-anxiolytic agent at low doses (Hen-Shoval et al., 2018). These findings in preclinical models are relevant because a substantial proportion of depressive patients are resistant to current antidepressants, and the EC system might “be a target for new anti-depressant drugs” (Shbiro et al., 2019). Some have also suggested that the combination of terpenes with cannabinoids to treat mood and anxiety disorders may be a good strategy (Ferber et al., 2020). In conclusion, CBD and other EC system active compounds have a myriad of polypharmacological mechanisms including 5-HT_{1A} activation and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis activity regulation with antidepressant, prohedonic, and anxiolytic effects that may be considered putative antidepressant drugs in the near future (Hen-Shoval et al., 2018). Endocannabinoids are closely related to HPA so that acute and chronic stress increases and decreases endocannabinoid levels, respectively (Sher, 2019). And the interaction between endocannabinoid and the HPA axis might play a critical role in the neurobiology of SB (Sher, 2019).

The objective of the present study is to explore the level of 4 endogenous cannabinoids (AEA; PEA; 2-AG; and, OEA) in SA, and the interaction of these endocannabinoids with biomarkers associated with stress, namely serum ACTH, cortisol, and β -endorphin. We hypothesized that compared to psychiatric controls (PC) who have never made a suicide attempt, SA will have higher levels of some endocannabinoids.

2 Experimental procedures

2.1 Sample and procedure

Patients were extracted from a larger sample of 65 SA and 13 PC evaluated at Puerta de Hierro University Hospital (Majadahonda, Madrid, Spain) between July 1, 2017 and November 15, 2019. The inclusion criteria were: 1) adult age and legally competent, 2) competency in the Spanish language, and 3) signed informed consent (either by the patient or the legal guardian). The exclusion criterion was any medical condition that causes endocrine disruption. The local Ethics Committee approved the study (IRB Number 11.17, June 12, 2017).

All patients were evaluated by interns in psychiatry using a protocol collecting socio-demographic and clinical variables (Baca-Garcia et al., 2006). We did not use test-retest measures because 90% of the protocols were taken by a single resident (JHH). Even so, the PI (HBF) had consensus meetings before the research was initiated and every two-three months with the residents (JHH, TPL, EGB) in order to sort out any doubts or problems they might have had regarding proceedings. The PI had also regular meetings with those responsible for the remaining collaborators. Patient medical records were reviewed to complete missing information. The main Axis I diagnoses were provided by the Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI) (Sheehan et al., 1998). Axis II disorders were clinically evaluated. A suicide attempt was defined as "a self-destructive behavior with intent to end one's life independent of resulting damage" (O'Carroll et al., 1996; Silverman et al., 2007). The protocol included the presence of non-suicidal-self-injury (NSSI), and of "high volume" NSSI (individuals with ≥ 15 lifetime NSSI) (Ness et al., 2016). Suicide risk was measured by the short version of the Personality and Life Event Scale (S-PLE), a 6-item instrument aimed at identifying individuals at risk of SB (Artieda-Urrutia et al., 2015).

2.2 Blood collection

Serum samples were collected from all patients between 7:30 AM and 8:30 AM. Later on, peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were obtained by centrifugation on a Ficoll-Hypaque gradient and frozen in liquid nitrogen (-196°C) until the assay for endocannabinoids. The laboratory personnel were blind to all clinical information.

2.3 Assays of ACTH, cortisol, β -endorphin levels and endocannabinoids

Controlling for age and gender, the levels of 8 (7.30–8.30) AM serum were assayed by: 1) ACTH and cortisol ($\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$): chemiluminescence; 2) β -endorphin (pg/mL): using a commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) Kit (byorbit, range: 10 pg/ml -2000 pg/ml) according to the manufacturer's instructions; and 3) endocannabinoids (pmol/ml): high resolution liquid chromatography with mass spectrometry.

2.4 Statistical analyses

Descriptive analysis was performed by means of absolute and relative frequencies for categorical variables and mean (standard deviation) for numerical variables. Univariable analyses were made with the chi-square or Fisher's exact tests for categorical variables, and Student's *t*-test and Pearson's correlations for continuous variables.

We used Levene's Test for Homogeneity of Variance. We used correlations to explore the linear relationship between two different biomarkers.

Significance level was established at $p < 0.05$. Given the limited sample size we also commented on those findings that were marginally non-significant ($p < 0.10$). The SPSS v. 20 software (Macintosh) was used for statistical analysis.

3 Results

3.1 Sociodemographic features

With the exception of those living in their household, there were no further statistically significant differences between the two groups with regard to sociodemographic characteristics (age, gender, and family income) (see Table 1).

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Table 1

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Sociodemographic features ($N = 42$).

	PC ($n = 12$)	SA ($n = 30$)	Total	χ^2	df	p-value
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)			
Sex						.078 (FET)
Male	7 (58.3)	8 (26.7)	15 (35.7)			
Female	5 (41.7)	22 (73.3)	27 (64.3)			
Living with				8.851	3	.035
Alone or single	0 (0.0)	8 (26.7)	8 (19.5)			
Friends	3 (27.3)	3 (3.3)	4 (9.8)			
Married or with partner	3 (27.3)	12 (40)	15 (36.6)			
Family of origin	5 (45.5)	9 (30)	14 (34.1)			
Nationality						1 (FET)
Spanish	8 (66.7)	21 (70)	29 (69)			
Other	4 (33.3)	1 (30)	3 (31)			
Socioeconomic level (> 1500 Euros/month)						1 (FET)
Yes	4 (66.7)	13 (56.5)	17 (58.6)			
Age	Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)	t	df	p-value
	34.33 (15.05)	40.40 (14.37)	38.67 (14.64)	-1.220	40	.230

PC: Psychiatric controls who have no history of previous suicide attempts; SA: Suicide attempters.

3.2 Personal and familial antecedents, and the S-PLE score

With the exception of familial antecedents of mental disorders, there was no difference between the two groups with regard to any other personal and familial antecedents (see Table 2). Furthermore, the S-PLE score was more elevated among SA compared with the PC group.

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Table 2

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Clinical features, personal and familial antecedents, and the S-PLE.

	PC ($n = 12$)	SA ($n = 30$)	TOTAL ($n = 42$)	χ^2	df	p-value
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)			
Familial antecedents of mental disorders (yes)	9 (100)	14 (50)	23 (62.2)			.007 (FET)
Medical antecedents (yes)	1 (8.3)	8 (26.7)	9 (21.4)			.247 (FET)
Psychiatric antecedents (yes)	10 (83.3)	21 (70)	31 (73.8)			.464 (FET)
Psychotropic medication use (yes)	10 (83.3)	25 (83.3)	35 (83.3)			1 (FET)
Previous psychiatric hospitalization (yes)	4 (50)	3 (33.3)	13 (37.1)			0.433 (FET)

Lifetime tobacco-alcohol-drug use (yes)	8 (66.7)	21 (70)	29 (69)			1 (FET)
History of past NSSI (yes)	3 (30)	6 (53.6)	18 (47.4)			.278 (FET)
High volume NSSI (>15 NSSI lifetime) (yes)	2 (20)	8 (28.6)	10 (26.3)			.699 (FET)
Axis I disorder (index episode) (yes)	10 (83.3)	23 (85.2)	33 (84.6)			1 (FET)
Axis II disorder (Yes) (index episode) (yes)	2 (41.7)	11 (40.7)	16 (41)			1 (FET)
	PC (n = 4)	SA (n = 23)	TOTAL (n = 27)	t	df	p-value
	Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)			
Number of Previous psychiatric hospitalizations	2 (0.81)	1.43 (2.55)	1.52 (2.37)	2.182	25	.152
	PC (n = 7)	SA (n = 26)	TOTAL (n = 33)	t	df	p-value
	Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)			
S-PLE score	2.22 (0.80)	2.75 (0.49)	2.65 (0.60)	-2.21	31	.0035

PC: Psychiatric controls who have no history of previous suicide attempts; SA: Suicide attempters; the Personality and Life Event Scale (S-PLE).

3.3 Major DSM-5 axis I diagnoses

There were no statistically significant differences regarding Axis I diagnoses between PC and SA (see Table 3).

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Table 3

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Main Axis I Diagnosis (index episode).

	PC (n = 12)	SA (n = 30)	TOTAL (n = 42)	χ^2	Df	p-value
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	2.748	6	.097
Major Depressive Disorder	2 (16.7)	7 (25.9)	9 (23.1)			
Adjustment Disorder	3 (25)	6 (22.2)	9 (23.1)			
Psychotic Disorder	3 (25)	3 (11.1)	6 (15.4)			
Bipolar Disorder	1 (8.3)	1 (3.7)	2(5.1)			
Obsessive Compulsive Disorder	0 (0)	1 (3.7)	1 (2.6)			
NO Axis I Diagnosis	2 (16.7)	4 (14.8)	2 (15.4)			

3.4 Biomarkers

Initially, we considered all patients in our analyses ($n = 42$; Table 4 and Fig. 1). Later on, we repeated the analyses after excluding those patients who either tested positive to cannabis use in urine or we could not confirm a negative test for cannabis in the urine test ($n = 28$; Table 5 and Fig. 2). Serum AEA and PEA levels were higher in SA in comparison to PC (see Tables 4 and 5 for statistical significance analyses). There was no difference between SA and PC with regard to cortisol and β -endorphin levels, but ACTH was statistically significantly higher among PC in comparison to SA (see Table 4 and 5).

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Table 4

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Serum biomarkers concentrations ($n = 42$) without controlling for cannabis use ($n = 42$).

	PC ($n = 12$)	SA ($n = 30$)	F	p-value
Endogenous cannabinoids				
AEA (pmol/ml) Mean (Sd)	1.62 (2.49)	3.58 (5.77)	3.043	.089
PEA (pmol/ml) Mean (Sd)	1.21 (1.20)	3.31 (4.82)	6.226	.017
OEA (pmol/ml) Mean (Sd)	0.98 (0.92)	0.89 (1.62)	−641	.428
2-AG (pmol/ml) Mean (Sd)	3.59 (4.92)	2.72 (4.40)	−0.565	.456
ACTH ($\mu\text{g/dl}$) Mean (Sd)	32.11 (21.60)	20.05 (9.96)	9.031	.005
Cortisol ($\mu\text{g/dl}$) Mean (Sd)	18.05 (7.12)	14.24 (6.87)	0.381	.568
β -endorphin (pg/mL) Mean (Sd)	165.45 (101.63)	118.11 (72.41)	1.240	.176

alt-text: Fig 1

Fig. 1

8 AM Endocannabinoid levels (pmol/ml) in psychiatric controls (PC) and suicide attempters (SA) without controlling for cannabis use ($n = 42$).

alt-text: Table 5

Table 5

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Serum biomarkers concentrations ($n = 28$).

	PC ($n = 7$)	SA ($n = 21$)	F	p-value
Endogenous cannabinoids				
AEA (pmol/ml) Mean (Sd)	0.64 (1.11)	4.57 (6.38)	4.852	.037
PEA (pmol/ml) Mean (Sd)	1.21 (1.25)	4.35 (5.46)	4.125	.053
OEA (pmol/ml) Mean (Sd)	1.35 (1.04)	1 (1.82)	0.347	.561

2-AG (pmol/ml) Mean (Sd)	2.17 (2.71)	3.32 (5.07)	0.685	.415
ACTH (µg/dl) Mean (Sd)	37.63 (25.25)	18.63 (9.11)	9.031	.005
Cortisol (µg/dl) Mean (Sd)	18.66 (6.75)	13.94 (5.90)	0.381	.568
β-endorphin (pg/mL) Mean (Sd)	139.04 (94.71)	125.29 (76.47)	0.243	.626

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Fig. 2

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8 AM Endocannabinoid levels (pmol/ml) in psychiatric controls (PC) and suicide attempters (SA) controlling for cannabis use ($n = 28$).

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Serum ACTH levels positively correlated with serum cortisol levels ($r = 0.528$, $p = 0.01$). Furthermore, serum AEA levels positively correlated with PEA levels ($r = 0.482$, $p = 0.01$).

4 Discussion

Consistent with the scarce literature available, the present study in SA suggest that endocannabinoids may play a relevant role in the pathophysiology of SB. We found virtually no statistically significant differences between PC and SA with regard to sociodemographic features, with the exception that SA were more likely to be living alone or single. Nor did we find statistically significant differences when comparing PC and SA regarding clinical features and major Axis I diagnoses, with the remarkable exception of a higher score on the S-PLE scale in SA. The S-PLE is a 6-item scale which has demonstrated a singular capacity in different studies to identify SA just by using 6 simple indirect questions (Artieda-Urrutia et al., 2015; Fernandez-Pelaez et al., 2017). In other words, 6 simple questions indirectly tackling SB can accurately identify subjects at risk of SB in less than 1 min, thus making this screening questionnaire very interesting for ER or Primary Care settings.

It is not surprising that interest is increasing concerning the role of the EC system in SB, given that cannabis “is the most widely used illicit substance worldwide” (Shalit et al., 2016). The use of cannabis has dramatically increased in recent years (Casajuana Köguel, López-Pelayo et al., 2018), particularly the use of synthetic cannabinoids (Shalit et al., 2016; Bassir Nia, Mann et al. 2019).

In spite of the growing use of cannabis worldwide, the relationship between the EC system and SB has scarcely been explored (Blasco-Fontecilla 2018). As we stressed in this editorial, the first suspicion of a relationship between the EC system and SB was suggested when rimonabant (a CB₁ receptor antagonist), which produced dysphoria, anxiety, and autolytic ideation in some obese patients, was withdrawn from the market in 2008 (Christensen et al., 2007). Furthermore, a recent population-based longitudinal study reported an association between heavy cannabis use and SB

among men but not women (Shalit et al., 2016). Finally, in another recent study comparing 13,986 twins (6181 monozygotic, 7805 dizygotic), those who had used cannabis compared to those who did not, the authors found that cannabis use was linked to: 1) a 100-times greater risk of suicidal ideation; and 2) an almost 7-times greater risk of attempted suicide (Agrawal et al., 2017). Furthermore, the authors warned that: 1) the use of cannabis increased from 30.4% in the 1st wave of the study (1992–1993) to 69% in the 3rd wave of the study (2005–2009) and 2) the average age of onset had fallen, while the frequency of use had risen.

In this context, our finding that serum AEA and PEA were higher among SA when compared to PC is remarkable. In a previous study of 34 combat veterans with ($n=17$) or without ($n=17$) a history of attempts, the authors found that 2-AG levels, but not AEA, were higher among veterans with a history of suicide attempts (Sher et al., 2019). Furthermore, serum 2-AG levels reported in this study were much higher than those found in our study. These authors reported that SA and non-attempters had mean 2-AG levels of 10.24 ± 4.51 and 7.89 ± 3.28 , respectively, much higher than the values reported in our study. Furthermore, the relevance of the 2-AG findings was negligible in our study. More importantly, we found that AEA levels were considerably higher in our sample, both in SA and PC when compared to the values reported by Sher and colleagues in combat veterans (0.84 in SA and 0.87 in non-SA) (Sher et al., 2019). Thus, we cannot assume their explanation that “looks like AEA reduces suicidality among SA, i.e., AEA is involved in the secondary prevention of a suicide attempt. AEA may reduce suicidality because the endocannabinoid system limits activation of the stress response through distributed actions in limbic and hypothalamic circuits in the brain” (Sher et al., 2019). Given that the authors measured these cannabinoids following a similar methodology and in similar conditions (i.e. fasting, 8 AM), differences could be attributed to a wide range of potential confounding factors. One possible explanation has to do with the clinical situation in which the patients were evaluated: in our study, both SA and PC were evaluated in the ER under a very stressful situation, either after a suicide attempt (in the case of SA), or after psychiatric decompensation leading to a psychiatric admission (regarding PC). On the other hand, Sher et al. enrolled 34 veterans who had or not a previous history of suicide attempt in the previous 5 years, and evaluated them under no stressful conditions. In other words, the contextual conditions in which both studies were carried out were completely different and may explain the divergent endocannabinoid results. Given that endocannabinoid levels increase in response to acute stress (Sher, 2019), it is not surprising that we found higher serum AEA levels; however, they reported higher 2-AG levels (Sher et al., 2019), which is intriguing.

These authors suggested that 2-AG, and not AEA, is “more biologically important endocannabinoid than AEA because it is present at a much higher concentration in tissues and displays greater efficacy at the target receptors than AEA” (Sher et al., 2019). Our study suggests, on the contrary, that AEA and PEA might be the more important endocannabinoids in SAs. Furthermore, we also found a strong, positive correlation between AEA and PEA levels ($r=0.482$, $p=0.01$). This might suggest that both endocannabinoids are critically involved in SB. Different authors have suggested that endocannabinoids play a role in the genesis of affective disorders and SB (Vinod and Hungund, 2006; Sher, 2019). However, findings are somewhat controversial. Thus, serum levels of 2-AG and AEA are decreased in PTSD, major depression, PTSD or after chronic stress, but there are also reports of increased 2-AG and AEA levels in minor depression and PTSD (Sher, 2019). In conclusion, it would be naïve or too ambitious to rate the “importance” of each of the endocannabinoids with the limited data we have on them and their role in the central nervous system and psychopathology to date.

Furthermore, several lines of evidence both in animal and human studies suggest that the stimulation of the EC system has antidepressant-like effects (Colino et al., 2018; Hen-Shoval et al., 2018). Accordingly, our finding of higher serum endocannabinoids levels, particularly AEA and PEA, in SAs may indicate a potential neuroprotective, buffering effect of endocannabinoids. However, in a study evaluating the quality of life among individuals with depressive disorders, cannabis users, compared to non-users, displayed higher rates of suicide attempts (Aspis et al., 2015). In any case, we have recently suggested (Colino et al., 2018) that endocannabinoids have great potential use as putative treatments for SB for at least the following reasons: 1) most people who attempt suicide suffer mental (psychological) pain (does anyone know a happy person who wants to pass away?) (Blasco-Fontecilla et al., 2015); 2) mental pain is what unifies and gives meaning to SB (de Leon et al., 2015); and 3) Sativex[®], an oromucosal spray with identical proportions of cannabidiol and 9-THC is approved for the treatment of different types of chronic pain, including central neuropathic pain in multiple sclerosis and intractable cancer pain (Hauser et al., 2017, Russo et al., 2016). To sum up, the role that endocannabinoids may play in the treatment of SB might be summarized in two simple words: hedonic (enhancement) and pain relief.

The major strength of our pilot study is that we demonstrated that apart from AEA and 2-AG, other serum endocannabinoids can be measured in clinical studies. Furthermore, we measured all biochemical markers in similar conditions for PC and SA. The major limitation of the current study is the small sample size, even though our study has a fair sample size if compared to similar studies carried out in the field (i.e. the study by Sher et al. compared 17 SA with 17 controls). This is not surprising given the complexity of measuring serum endocannabinoids. Furthermore, our study suffers from the typical limitations of retrospective studies.

In conclusion, our study presents preliminary evidence about the role of 4 endocannabinoids, and particularly, AEA and PEA in SA. Our results should be interpreted with caution. As we have stressed, the elevation of AEA and PEA can be explained by the acute contextual situation in which SA were evaluated. However, PC were also evaluated under pretty similar conditions. Furthermore, our results were not affected when we excluded all the patients in whom we had no negative urine test for cannabis, thus giving further support to our analyses. Finally, further studies on serum endocannabinoids and the interactions with stress and opioid systems, among others, may improve our understanding of SB.

Uncited references

[Dent et al., 1981](#), [Antunes et al., 2016](#), [Sha et al., 2016](#).

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Contributors

HBF designed the study and wrote the protocol. JHH, EGB, and TPL recruited all patients and filled-out the protocols. HBF managed the literature searches. SOG and JM managed endocannabinoid analyses. SR and ASL processed the samples at the biobank. HBF undertook the statistical analysis, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. All authors contributed to and have approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

In the last 24 months, Hilario Blasco-Fontecilla received lecture fees from Shire. He is Principal Investigator (PI) of an iPFIS research contract (www.isciii.es; IFI16/00,039) and co-PI of a MINECO research grant (RTI2018-101,857-B-I00); recipient of: 1) a FIPSE Grant, and 2) an IDIPHIPSA intensification Grant; involved in two clinical trials (MENSIA KOALA, NEWROFEED Study; ESKETSUI2002); member of the Advisory Board of ITA Salud Mental. Fernando [Sanchez](#)-Sanchez is an employee of TEA ediciones. Maria Rodrigo Yanguas is the recipient of an iPFS research contract (www.isciii.es). The remaining authors do not have any conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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 The corrections made in this section will be reviewed and approved by a journal production editor. The newly added/removed references and its citations will be reordered and rearranged by the production team.

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Highlights

- Suicide attempters have higher levels of serum anandamide (AEA) and N-palmitoiletanolamida (PEA) than psychiatric controls after controlling for cannabis use ($p = 0.037$, and $p = 0.053$, respectively).
- Serum AEA levels positively correlated with PEA levels ($r = 0.482$, $p = 0.01$).
- Our findings suggest that some endocannabinoids may play a role in the pathophysiology of SB.

Queries and Answers

Q1

Query: Please confirm that givennames and surnames have been identified correctly.

Answer: Yes

Q2

Query: AU:Please provide a definition for the significance of [bold] in tables 1,2.

Answer: In both cases (Nationality, and socioeconomic level), the p-value was 1 (or 1.000) (FET). In other words, it was statistically non-significant.

Q3

Query: The references 'Hauser et al., 2017; Russo et al., 2016' are cited in the text but is not listed in the references list. Please either delete the in-text citations or provide full reference details following journal style.

Answer: Please, do include both references:

Häuser, W., Petzke, F., Fitzcharles, M.A., 2018. Efficacy, tolerability and safety of cannabis-based medicines for chronic pain management - An overview of systematic reviews. *Eur J Pain*. 22(3):455-470.

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Q4

Query: This section comprises references that occur in the reference list but not in the body of the text. Please position each reference in the text or, alternatively, delete it.

Answer: WE have deleted all unnecessary references.

Q5

Query: Please check funding information and confirm its correctness.

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